

www.bjisrd.com

“Mukhammas” As a Special Genre in New Uzbek Poetry

Nazarova Dildora Ilhomovna,

Bukhara State Medical Institute, doctor of philosophy (PhD), associate professor

***Abstract:** The presented research article is based on comparative-contrastive and structural-typological analyses, the study of the features of the narrative structure of the Uzbek novel of the twentieth century by identifying compositional and stylistic patterns will allow, on the one hand, to determine its national artistic originality in the system of world literature, and on the other hand, to more fully present the development of new Uzbek poetry of the XX-XXI century from the point of view of the specifics of the poetics of the new novel genre, reflecting the general trends of modern world literature.*

The scientific paper also presents numerous verses of poems of renowned Uzbek poets of last century to reflect the illustrativeness of the poetic content being analyzed in the given article.

***Key words:** lyrics, genre, mukhammas, poem, lines, metaphors, verses.*

Introduction.

In the conditions of state independence, Uzbek literary studies within the field of new developing poetry have faced new challenges in the study of theoretical and historical-literary problems. At present, Uzbek literature has taken the position of an independent subject in the system of "world literature", which has not only entailed a change in its external parameters, but has also significantly affected the methodological approaches to its study. The global nature of the increasing interpenetration of literatures has set certain tasks for researchers, the solution of which confirms the idea that an isolated study of Uzbek literature today cannot provide comprehensive solutions and results.

Main part

It is known that mukhammas is one of the most common lyrical genres in classical literature, and it is of two types: independent mukhammas and takhmismukhammas. E. Vahidov, J. Kamal have both types. E. Vahidov's "Ajab ermas" puzzle is written in a delightful style:

Бу кунлар катта йўлда
Бир довон ўлса ажаб эрмас,
Муқаррар ортида йўл
Кенг, равон бўлса ажаб эрмас,
Ватанга сидку имон,
Имтиҳон бўлса ажаб эрмас,
Фаровон юрту олам,
Тинч жаҳон бўлса ажаб эрмас,
Биз этган барча орзулар
Аён ўлса ажаб эрмас.

As is known, Zavkiy's famous poem "Ajab Ermas" attracts attention because it expresses the dreams of the people who dream of a new system. The reason is that the poet, like many others, pinned great hopes on the October Revolution. Therefore, he looked to the future with a spirit of confidence and wrote hopeful lines. E.Vohidov's poem was written during the days of independence. The poem is filled with feelings of gratitude for independence. Therefore, the long road is the road to independence. There are many paths to achieving it. The poet has great hopes for independence and wants its path to be wide and smooth.

Сен эй, сен она юртим,
Кўхна-ю ёш Ўзбекистоним,
Ҳамиша сен ўзингсан
Боиси ашъор-у достоним,
Гурурим, номусим, шодлик, ғамим,
Обод-у пайҳоним
Кўтар бошингни мағрур,
Ҳақлисан, шавкатли деҳқоним,
Бошингда шиша янглиғ
Осмон бўлса ажаб эрмас.

The following lines are connected with the description of the Motherland. When the poet says “My old and young Uzbekistan,” he means the past and present of the Motherland. Because young Uzbekistan is a sign of its independence. E.Vohidov sincerely dreams that the sky will become crystal clear due to independence. The poet ends the poem in a very uplifting spirit:

(Ки Завқий орзу этган
Замон бўлса ажаб эрмас)
Етиб етмишга Эркин
Навқирон ўлса ажаб эрмас.

Indeed, it is clear that Zavqi wanted to see his country free when he finished his hopeful lines. This is what the poet means, and he is happy that the thousand-year-old dream of our people has come true, and even though he is in his seventies, he feels lonely.

Jamal Kamal's poem "Fayzulla Khojaev's eyes" belongs to an independent collection:

Ажаб бир суврате, дўстлар, боқиб мен ҳар сафар дилсўз,
Ажаб бир чакнаган сиймо, ажаб бир порлаган юлдуз,
Бу кўзлар бунчалар шахло, бу кўзлар мунчалар маъюс,
Бу кўзлар айласа ҳар неки ошкору ниҳон айлар,
Бу кўзлар имтиҳон айлар, бу кўзлар имтиҳон айлар.

The metaphors used in relation to Fayzulla Khojaev, such as “a shining figure”, “a shining star”, are interesting. They reflect the external appearance and inner world of the historical figure. The rhyme is traditionally rhymed: b-b-b-a-a, v-v-v-a-a, g-g-g-a-a, etc. Jamal Kamal’s second group of rhymes are related to the ghazals of Navoi, Babur, Fuzuli, Mashrab, and are called tahmis rhymes. In this respect, the rhyme associated with Navoi’s ghazal is noteworthy:

Йўқ, чақиндин эрмас ул, осмон қизил, сориг, яшил,
Ё шафақдин ҳар тараф рахшон қизил, сориг, яшил,
Ё чаманда лолаю райҳон қизил, сориг, яшил,
Хилъатин то айламиш жонон қизил, сориг, яшил,
Шуълайи оҳим чиқар ҳар ён қизил, сориг, яшил.(90)

If the poet slightly changed the traditional rhyming pattern in his independent verses, he completely preserved the traditionality in the tahmis verse. That is, the rhymes are observed in the form of a-a-a-a-a, b-b-b-a-a, v-v-v-a-a. In this romantic verse, the beloved and her external beauty are described.

S. Sayyid's verses in this respect belong to the second spirit. The poet connected verses to the ghazals of Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Babur, and Zakirjon Furkat. Therefore, the poet connected the following tahmis to Alisher Navoi's ghazal, which begins with "Zulfung achilib orazi diljo bila hikdar":

Кўнглим очилиб, ўйлаки орзу била ўйнар.
Кўрганда юзинг, орзуси қайғу била ўйнар,
Қайғуси яна завқ ила туйғу била ўйнар.
Зулфунг очилиб орази дилжў била ўйнар,
Ҳинду бачае шўхтурур у била ўйнар.

If you pay attention, the poet has completed the lines following the rules of connecting the words. That is, the verses quoted above the ghazal verse are consistent with Navoi's verses in terms of content and form. First, the first stanza of the ghazal is cross-rhymed. The poet adapted the three added verses accordingly. Secondly, Navoi's ghazal was written in Ramal Bahr. The poet also kept his weight.

Let's look at the next verse of the poem:

Кечдим шу замон қолган умр, бори ҳавасдин,

Жон куйди-ю, фарқ қолмади дил бирла нафасдин,
 Кўнглим отилиб, ишвасидин, чиқа қафасдин,
 Ул шўх кўнгил лавҳин этиб тийра нафасдин,
 Бир тифлдур, алқиссаки кўзгу била ўйнар.

As is known, in the later verses of the ghazal, the paired lines rhyme with each other. In the case of muhammas, the first four lines rhyme in the subsequent verses, and the fifth line rhymes with the first verse. Thus, the words hawasdin, nafasdin, kafasdin, nafasdin create a melodious harmony.

It is evident that S. Sayyid Navoi was able to connect a muhammas appropriate to the weight and content of each verse of his ghazal.

The muhammas that the poet connected to Babur's ghazal, which begins with "Bahor ayomidur daghi yigitlikning avonidur", also has content and formal perfection:

Булут эрмас, кўк узра таркаган кўнгил гумонидур,
 Гумон қилмак бу дамда бегумон дилнинг зиёнидур.
 Кўкарган хор ила хаслар тирикликнинг нишонидур,
 Баҳор айёмидур дағи йигитликнинг авонидур.
 Кетур соқий, шароби нобким, ишрат замонидур.

Conclusion

As noted above, the first stanza rhymes with each other. Babur's ghazal is written in the musamma style of the poem. Thus, the poet maintained the weight in connecting the verses. In general, during the years of independence, our poets worked effectively in the genre of verses, one of the active genres of classical literature. It is observed that these verses reflect the thoughts and feelings of our contemporaries and the hymns of independence.

References:

1. Kamol J. Yana konglimda ul oy. – Tashkent: “Meriyus”, 2010, p. 89.
2. Hakqulov I. Rubaiyat in Uzbek literature. – Tashkent: Fan, 1981. – p. 100.
3. Ochilov E. Historical development of the rubaiyat genre \ “Uzbek language and literature”, 2006, issue 4, p. 38.
4. Nazarova D.I. The interpretation of educational ideas in the poems of Jamal Kamal// International Scientific Journal Theoretical & Applied Science.- 2019.- №11.- P. 136 – 138.
5. Nazarova D.I. Literary Motives of Sufizm and Spiritual, Moral Ideas in the Lyrics of Jamal Kamal//International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE).-2019.- №10.– P. 223 - 225.
6. Dilrabo Quvvatova, Nazarova D.I. The rubai genre in the works of Jamal Kamal// The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations.- 2020.- №9.- P. 346 - 352.
7. Nazarova D.I. Jamol Kamolning Asru radifli g’azaliga yozgan muxammasi// Ilim ham ja'miyet. Ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal.– 2020.- №1.– Б. 93 - 94

8. Nazarova D.I. The foundation of Kamol Jamol's poems is pain// Conference of Management of Islamic Education Leadership In The Era of Revolution.- 2020.- №6.– P. 1 - 3.
9. Nazarova D.I. Feelings of lyric heroes in Kamol Jamol's work// Conference of Management of Islamic Education Leadership In The Era of Revolution.– 2020.- №6.– P. 1 - 3.